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Domestic Fowl Eggshell: Its Lipid Profiles [Crude Fat, Fatty Acids, Sterols, Phospholipids] and Health Indices

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Abstract

This study reports on the chromatographic determination of the crude fat (CF), fatty acids (FAs), sterols (STs), phospholipids (PLs) and the nutrient fat health indices: atherogenicity index (AI), thrombogenicity index (TI), hypocholesterolemic/hypercholesterolemic (H/h) ratio, health promoting index (HPI), unsaturation index (UI), EPA+DHA, flesh lipid quality (FLQ), LA/ALA ratio, PUFA/SFA ratio, trans-fatty acid (TFA), peroxidizability index (PI) in the eggshells of the free range domestic fowl lipid content. The classic indices such as Σ SFA, Σ MUFA, Σ PUFA, Σ n-6 PUFA, Σ TFA, Σ UFA, and n-6 PUFA/ n-3 PUFA were used to calculate the health indices. The data from the CF, FAs, STs, PLs, classic indices and the health indices were discussed and compared with literature values, their health implications to likely direct/indirect consumers of the domestic fowl eggshells.

Keywords: Chicken Eggshells; Lipid Components; Fat Nutrient Health Indices

Introduction

Dietary fat is a member of the macronutrients including carbohydrates and proteins. Fat contents are known as triglycerides which are esters of three fatty acid chains and the alcohol glycerol. Fat content functions as energy deposits, protective padding as well as provides insulation against body heat temperature losses [1].

Fatty acids (FAs) are organic acids with at least one carboxyl ($-C(=O)OH$, $-COOH$, or CO_2H) group with a long carbon chain that has links that can be double bonds, e.g. unsaturated FAs, or single bonds, e.g. saturated FAs. FAs are derivations from triglycerides and phospholipids and are the main components of dietary fats. Most naturally occurring FAs have an unbranched chain of an even number (4-28) of carbon atoms. As depicted by the number of double bonds, the FA catalogue includes saturated fatty acids (SFAs), monounsaturated fatty acid (MUFA) and polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) [2]. As biological compounds, FAs play critical roles in human metabolism,

health and disease. Epidemiological studies as well as clinical trials showed that FAs are associated with cardiovascular diseases [3], neurological diseases [4], non-alcoholic fatty liver disease [5], allergic diseases [6], etc.

Fatty acids play positive or negative roles in the prevention and treatment of diseases. In general, FAs are obtained from various dietary sources that possess characteristic FA composition and consequently influence health outcome. From this perspective, the FA composition should be assessed to determine their nutritional and/or medicinal value. In this study therefore, both classic indices such as Σ SFA, Σ MUFA, Σ PUFA, Σ n-6 PUFA, Σ TFA, Σ UFA and n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA as well as nutrient fat health indices such as AI, TI, H/h, HPI, UI, EPA+DHA, FLQ, LA/ALA, PUFA/SFA, TFA and PI were reported and discussed as appropriate.

Phospholipids (PLs) are a diverse group of lipids characterized by the presence of one or more phosphate-containing moieties. These molecules possess both hydrophilic and hydrophobic regions, making them amphipathic and enabling the formation of lipid bilayers that constitute the foundation of biological membranes. In addition to their structural role, phospholipids participate in several cellular processes, including membrane signaling and regulation of cellular functions. The most prevalent phospholipids in living organisms are **glycerophospholipids**, which are built upon a glycerol backbone. Important members of this class include **phosphatidylcholine (PC)**, **phosphatidylserine (PS)**, **lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC)**, **phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)**, and **phosphatidylinositol (PI/PtdIns)**, all of which contribute significantly to membrane architecture and cellular activities [7].

Plant and animal sterols are lipids found in cell membranes with similar basic structures but differ in specific side chain modifications. Animal cells primarily contain cholesterol (a zoosterol). Sterols are vital to cell membrane fluidity and function, serving as hormone precursors and signaling molecules. Cholesterol is the dominant animal sterol; it has a simple side chain without the C-24 alkylation seen in phytosterols. Cholesterol functions as a precursor to fat-soluble vitamins and steroid hormones [8]. Cholesterol is often equimolar with phospholipids in many

Domestic fowl, commonly referred to as poultry, are domesticated bird species maintained for the production of meat, eggs, feathers, and in some cases for ornamental value. These birds originated from wild jungle fowl, with the chicken representing the most widespread and economically important form. Modern chickens are believed to have evolved primarily from the red jungle fowl (*Gallus gallus*), a species native to regions of South and Southeast Asia, particularly India and neighboring countries [9,10]. Poultry farming has become a major component of global agriculture, with the worldwide chicken population surpassing 26.5 billion birds in 2023, while annual production for human consumption exceeds 50 billion birds [11]. Egg-laying hens are highly productive and may yield more than 300 eggs annually under appropriate management conditions. Beyond their agricultural significance, chickens have long held cultural, religious, and literary importance in many civilizations. Taxonomically, the domestic chicken belongs to the Kingdom Animalia, Phylum Chordata, Class Aves, Order Galliformes, Family Phasianidae, Genus *Gallus*, and is classified as the subspecies *Gallus gallus domesticus*, first described by

Linnaeus (1758).

A chicken eggshell is the hard, outer protective layer of an egg, primarily composed of calcium carbonate crystals (about 94-96%) held together by an organic matrix. Shell is semi-permeable and allows for gas and water exchange through pores while also providing a barrier against bacteria and damage. Eggshells contain essential minerals, like Ca, Mg and P, and can be reused for various purposes, such as Ca supplements for chickens or as a catalyst in chemical reactions [12, 13]. The US food industry generates 150,000 tons of shell waste per year [14]. The disposal methods for waste eggshells are 26.6% as fertilizer, 21.1% as animal feed ingredients, 26.3% discarded in municipal dumps and 15.8% used in other ways [15]. Due to their CaCO₃ content, eggshells have the potential to be used as raw material in the production of lime [16]. The rich CaCO₃ shell has been used in the application for Ca deficiency therapies in humans and animals [15, 17]. A single eggshell has a mass of 6 grams which yields 2200 mg of calcium ($6000 \text{ mg} \times 0.95 \times 0.4 = 2280 \text{ mg}$). Eggshell particles are used in toothpaste as an anti-tartar agent [15]. Powdered eggshells have been used for bone mineralization and growth [15, 17, 18]. Recent applications of eggshells include producing calcium lactate as a firming agent, a flavour enhancer, a leavening agent, a nutrient supplement, a stabilizer, and thickener [15, 18]. Eggshells are also used as a calcium supplement in orange juice [14]. Froning and Bergquist [19] blended eggshell (70%) with technical albumin (8%), maize (5%), soya-bean meal (17%) and propionic acid (0.15%); blend was extruded, cooled and fed to laying hens as a protein and calcium supplement in a fully formulated diet. Hens fed the extrudate were not adversely affected in comparison to control birds (rate of lay, feed conversion, mortality, shell thickness and shell strength). Ihekoronye and Ngoddy [20] had discussed the composition of the hen's egg made up of three major component parts: shell, the white or albumen and the yolk. The shell had been shown to be composed of cuticle, spongy calcareous layer and mammillary layer whereas the membrane was said to be made up of air cell, outer shell membrane and inner shell membrane. Also, the shell constituted about 95.1% inorganic matter, 3.3% protein and 1.6% of the total hen's egg based on wet weight.

While dietary FAs affect the FA composition of the egg yolk, their direct presence in the eggshell itself is not a focus of research, which primarily investigates the role of lipids in the eggshell membrane's structure and function. FAs can play a role in the formation and quality of the membrane, which in turn affects the overall eggshell quality.

The eggshell membrane contains proteins and other substances that are regulated by lipid metabolism.

Eggshell waste therefore does have a theoretical value as an animal feed or as a fertilizer or lime substitute. In many countries, it is an acceptable practice for eggshells to be dried and used as a source of calcium in animal feeds. The recycling of the nutrients of eggshells back to the animals portends that the nutritional composition of the eggshells should be evaluated in terms of quantity and quality. Adeyeye [21] had made a comparative study on the characteristics of eggshells of some bird species. Fat is a member of the macronutrients and since eggshells are often recycled in animal feeds, it is important to study the lipid profile of the hen's eggshells; hence, the purpose of this study is a simultaneous evaluation of the FAs classic indices, nutrient fat health indices, sterols and phospholipids in the hen's eggshells.

Materials and Methods

Collection and treatment of samples

The hens' eggs were directly obtained from poultry keeper. Five eggs were involved in the study and they were collected at once. The eggs were cooked to be able to easily remove the shell. The shells were then oven-dried and ground into powder, sieved using 200 mm mesh and kept in the freezer in McCartney bottles pending analysis. Free range hens' eggshells were used for the evaluations made.

Proximate analysis

The crude fat value was determined according to A.O.A.C. method 920.39A [22]. The crude fat value was used to calculate the theoretical total fatty acids by multiplying with a conversion factor of 0.83 (for poultry) [23]. The calorific value in kcal was by multiplying the crude fat and the calculated total fatty acids by 9 in each case [24].

Preparation of methyl esters and analysis

About 0.25 g of the aliquot was weighed into the extraction thimble for lipid extraction, the extraction lasted for 5-6 h. About 50 mg of the extracted oil was saponified for 5 min at 95°C with 3.4 ml of 0.5 M KOH in dry methanol. The mixture was neutralised by 0.7 M HCl. Three ml (3 ml) of 14% boron trifluoride in methanol was added [22]. The mixture was heated for 5 min at 90°C to achieve complete methylation. The fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were 3 × extracted from the mixture with redistilled n-hexane. The content was concentrated to 1 ml for analysis and 1 µl was injected into the injection pot of GC. The FAMES were analysed using an HP 5890 GC powered with HP ChemStation rev. A09.01 [1206] software (GMI,

Minnesota, USA) fitted with a flame ionization detector. Nitrogen was the carrier gas with a flow rate of 20-60 ml/min. The oven programme was: initial temperature at 60°C, first ramping at 10°C/min for 20 min, maintained for 4 min, second ramping at 15°C/min for 4 min and maintained for 10 min. The injection temperature was 250°C whilst the detector temperature was 320°C. A capillary column (30 m, 0.25 mm) packed with a polar compound (HP INNOWAX) with diameter (0.25 µm) was used to separate the esters. Split injection type was used having a split ratio of 20:1. The peaks were identified by comparison with standards of fatty acid methyl esters.

Sterol analysis

Sterol was analysed for as described by [22]. The aliquot of the extracted fat was added to the screw-capped test tubes. The sample was saponified at 90°C for 30 min, using 3 ml of 10% KOH in ethanol, to which 0.2 ml of benzene had been added to ensure miscibility. Deionized water (3 ml) was added and 1 ml of hexane was used in extracting the non-saponifiable materials.

Phospholipids analysis

The method of [25] was employed in the analysis of phospholipids. 1.00 E-2 g of the extracted fat was added to each test tube. To ensure complete dryness of the fat for phospholipids analysis, the solvent was completely removed by passing stream of nitrogen gas on the fat. 4.00 E-1 ml chloroform was added to the tube followed by the addition of 1.00 E-1 ml chromogenic solution. The tube was heated at 100°C in water bath for 1 min, 20 sec. The content was allowed to cool to the laboratory temperature and 5 ml hexane was added and the tube shaken gently several times. The solvent and the aqueous layers were allowed to separate. The hexane layer was recovered and concentrated to 1.0 ml for analysis. The phospholipids were analysed using an HP 5890 powered with HP gas chromatography (HP 5890 powered with HP ChemStation rev. A09.01 [1206] software [GMI, Inc., Minnesota, USA]) fitted with a pulse flame photometric detector. Nitrogen was used as the carrier gas with a flow rate of 20-60 ml/min. The oven programme was initial temperature at 50°C whilst the detector temperature was 320°C. A capillary column (30 m, 0.25 mm) packed with a polar compound (HP) with a diameter (0.25 µm) was used to separate the phospholipids. Split injection type was used having a split ratio of 20:1. The peaks were identified by comparison with standard phospholipids [25].

Quality assurance

Standard chromatograms were prepared for FAMES, STLs and PLDs which were then compared with respective analytical results; calibration curves were prepared for all the standard mixtures and correlation coefficient determined for each FA parameter, same for each ST and each PLD. Correlation coefficient should be ≥ 0.95 for the result to be acceptable. It was performed with Hewlett Packard Chemistry (HPCHEM) software (GMI, Inc., 6511 Bunker Lake Blvd Ramsey, Minnesota, 55303, USA).

Lipid quality indices

The various lipid quality indices were calculated as follows.

A. Antherogenic index (AI) was calculated according to [26]: $AI = [(4 \times C14:0) + C16:0] / [(n-6 \text{ PUFA} + n-3 \text{ PUFA}) + MUFA]$.

B. Thrombogenicity index (TI) was calculated according to [26]: $TI = [C14:0 + C16:0 + C18:0] / [0.5 \times MUFA + 0.5 \times n-6 \text{ PUFA} + 3 \times n-3 \text{ PUFA} + (n-3/n-6 \text{ PUFA})]$.

C. Hypocholesterolemic/hypercholesterolemic (H/h) ratio was calculated according to [27]: $H/h = [C18:1n-9 + C18:1n-7 + C18:2n-6 + C18:3n-6 + C18:3n-3 + C20:3n-3 + C20:4n-6 + C22:2n-6] / [C14:0 + C16:0]$.

D. The peroxidizability index (PI) was determined according to [28]: $PI = (\text{monoenoate} \times 0.025) + (\text{dienoate} \times 1) + (\text{trienoate} \times 2) + (\text{tetraenoate} \times 4) + (\text{pentaenoate} \times 6) + (\text{hexaenoate} \times 8)$.

E. EPA + DHA = $C22:6n-3 + C20:5n-3$.

F. PUFA/SFA = $n-6 + n-3 \text{ PUFA} / \text{SFA}$.

G. Health-promoting index (HPI) was proposed by [29]: $HPI = \sum \text{UFA} / [C12:0 + (4 \times C14:0) + C16:0]$.

H. Unsaturation index (UI) was calculated according to [30]: $UI = 1 \times (\% \text{monoenoics}) + 2 \times (\% \text{dienoics}) + 3 \times (\% \text{trienoics}) + 4 \times (\% \text{tetraenoics}) + 5 \times (\% \text{pentaenoics}) + 6 \times (\% \text{hexaenoics})$.

I. Trans fatty acid: ΣTFA .

J. LA/ALA ratio.

K. Fish lipid quality/flesh lipid quality (FLQ): $100 \times (C22:6n-3 + C20:5n-3) / \Sigma \text{FA}$

L. n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA ratio.

M. ALA/LA.

Conversion of FAs into edible portion (EP g/100 g)

$EP \text{ g}/100 \text{ g} = \text{individual FA} \times \text{TFA}/100 \text{ g} = X \text{ g}/100 \text{ g}$

where TFA = total fatty acid [23].

Results

Crude fat analysis of the chicken eggshells

The hen's eggshell crude fat value with its equivalent energy (kcal/100 g) are shown in Table 1. The crude fat (CF) is low at 2.55 g/100 g. When the CF got converted to total fatty acids (TFAs), the value obtained was 2.1165 g/100 g, the balance value from the CF was 0.4335 g/100g which was labelled as other lipids (OLs); these are likely comprised of phospholipids, sterols, vitamins, etc. Hence the trend is: $CF/TFA/OLs \text{ (g}/100 \text{ g)} = 2.55 > 2.1165 > 0.4335$ respectively with the corresponding energy (kcal/100 g) values of $22.95 > 19.05 > 3.902$ respectively. The TFA/CF (%) was high at 83.0 but low in OLs/CF (%) with value of 17.0 but OLs/TFA (%) was in-between at 20.48. It is observed that percentage energy values were similar to the quantity (column) percentages as appropriate.

Table 1. Crude fat analysis of the chicken eggshells

S / N	Parameter	Quantity	Energy (kcal/100 g)	% energy
1	Crude fat (CF) (g/100g)	2.55	22.95	—
2	CF * 0.83 (= TFA) (g/100g)	2.1165	19.05	—
3	CF - TFA (= OLs) (g/100g)	0.4335	3.902	—
4	TFA/CF (%)	83.0	—	83.0
5	OLs/CF (%)	17.0	—	17.0
6	OLs/TFA (%)	20.48	—	20.48

TFA = total fatty acid; OLs = other lipids; 0.83 = conversion of CF to TFA multiplication (i.e. 0.83 is a conversion factor of egg CF to TFA)

The fatty acid group profiles (Table 2)

The saturated fatty acid (SFA) group has a total value of 31.872561% (of total fatty acids, FAs). FAs of highest contribution came from C16:0 (19.100282%) and C18:0 (12.750989%).

The trans-monounsaturated FAs group was made up of C18:1 trans-6, C18:1 trans-9 and C18:1 trans-11; each exhibited $< 0.001\%$ concentration. Total T-MUFA was $1.22021 \times 10^{-5}\%$.

The cis-MUFA FAs group has many FAs of significantly high values as well as significantly low values. In the high values group were C16:1 cis-9, C18:1 cis-6 and C18:1 cis-9 whereas C14:1 cis-9 and C22:1 cis-13 were each of extremely low concentration. Total cis-MUFA concentration was 44.959092%.

The n-6 PUFA group was completely dominated by C18:2 cis-9,12 with value of 21.092293% out of a total value of 22.46158%. Other members of this group with value of > 0.10% were C20:2 cis-11,14 (0.239386%) and C20:4 cis-5,8,11,14 (1.042339%).

The n-3 PUFA group has only one member whose value was greater than 0.10% and that was C18:3 cis-9,12,15 with just 0.706727%.

Table 2. Fatty acid group profiles

S/N	Fatty acid group	Value (% of total fatty acid)
1.	SFA	
	(a) C12:0	0.000016
	(b) C14:0	0.021221
	(c) C16:0	19.100282
	(d) C18:0	12.750989
	(e) C24:0	0.000053
	(f) Total	31.87261
2.	MUFA (trans)	
	(a) C18:1 trans-6	4.10385E-6
	(b) C18:1 trans-9	2.65519E-7
	(c) C18:1 trans-11	7.83266E-6
	(d) Total	1.22021E-5
3.	MUFA (cis)	
	(a) C14:1 cis-9	2.40E-5
	(b) C16:1 cis-9	1.626052
	(c) C18:1 cis-6	19.893537
	(d) C18:1 cis-9	22.70339
	(e) C20:1 cis-11	0.736118
	(f) C22:1 cis-13	2.20E-5
	(g) Total	44.959092
4.	N-6 PUFA	
	(a) C18:2 cis-9,12	21.092293
	(b) C18:3 cis-6,9,12	0.087462
	(c) C20:2 cis-11,14	0.239386
	(d) C20:3 cis-8,11,14	6.10E-5
	(e) C20:4 cis-5,8,11,14	1.042339
	(f) C22:2 cis-13,16	3.90E-5
	(g) Total	22.46158

S/N	Fatty acid group	Value (% of total fatty acid)
5.	N-3 PUFA	
	(a) C18:3 cis-9,12,15	0.706723

Fatty acid groups as food

The various group FAs as calculated as food have been tabulated in Table 3. The total food equivalent was 2.1165 g/100 g. Major contributors to this value were SFA, MUFA (cis) and n-6 PUFA. The food value contribution is a reflection of the total FAs content of each group.

Table 3: Fatty acid groups as food (EPg/100g)

S/N	Fatty acid group	Quantity (%)	Quantity (EPg/100g)
1.	SFA	31.87256	0.6746
2.	MUFA (trans)	1.22021E-5	2.58257447E-7
3.	MUFA (cis)	44.959092	0.9515591822
4.	N-6 PUFA	22.46158	0.4753993407
5.	N-3 PUFA	0.706727	0.014957877
6.	Total	100	2.1165

EPg/100g = edible portion/100g

Insignificant FAs in the hen’s eggshells

Each FA in this group has FA value of < 0.001%. In fact the range was 9.29475 E-7 to 7.52740 E-6%. Total FAs value was 2.09229E-5 with corresponding food value of 4.42833000E-7 g/100 g.

Table 4. Insignificant fatty acids in the chicken eggshells sample [without MUFA trans]

S/N	Fatty acid	Quantity (%)	Quantity (EPg/100g)
1.	C6:0	0.0000	
2.	C8:0	0.0000	
3.	C10:0	0.0000	
4.	C18:2t-9, cis-12	3.44093E-6	
5.	C22:0	7.52740E-6	
6.	C20:3cis-11,14,17	4.99078E-6	

S/N	Fatty acid	Quantity (%)	Quantity (EPg/100g)
7.	C20:5cis-5,8,11,14,17	1.97203E-6	
8.	C24:1cis-15	9.29475E-7	
9.	C22:6cis-4,7,10,13,16,19	2.06230E-6	
10.	Total	2.09229E-5	4.42833000E-7

Health indices of the FAs in chicken eggshells

Depicted in Table 5 were the health indices of the FAs of the hen's eggshells. The IA value of 0.2816 is low but favourable. The IT is < 1.00 at 0.889 which is slightly high. The H/h value of 2.399 shows the ratio to be nutritionally high and nutritionally favourable. The UI is an indication that the eggshells of hen are moderately unsaturated and may likely be less rancid on the shell for a long time. The EPA+DHA and FLQ showed hen's eggshells to be deficient in the EPA+DHA, hence hen's eggshells can't be relied on to furnish the body with these FAs. The ratio of LA/ALA is high at 29.84503; this is because the value of ALA is very low, also seen in n-6/n-3 PUFA at 31.824611. The eggshell's SFA > PUFA, hence PUFA/SFA < 1.00. However, the value of 0.7269 is close to 1.00. The trans FA value was 1.2202E-5%, was low and is of no nutritional value other than the fact that the body does not require trans FAs at any quantity. The PI value was 28.2135513. This means the hen's eggshells oil has very low potential for peroxidation due to low value of ALA and trace levels of EPA and DHA.

Table 5. Health indices of the fatty acids in the chicken eggshells

S/N	Health indices full name	Index	Index value
1.	Index of atherogenicity	IA	0.2816
2.	Index of thrombogenicity	IT	0.889
3.	Hypocholesterolemic/hypercholesterolemic ratio	H/H	2.399
4.	Health-promoting index	HPI	3.551
5.	Unsaturation index	UI	94.1746
6.	Sum of eicosapentaenoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid	EPA+DHA	4.0343 E-6
7.	Fish lipid quality/flesh lipid quality	FLQ	4.0343 E-6

S/N	Health indices full name	Index	Index value
8.	Linoleic acid/ α -linolenic acid ratio	LA/ALA	29.84503
9.	Polyunsaturated fatty acid /saturated fatty acid ratio	PUFA/SFA	0.7269
10.	Trans fatty acid	TFA	1.2202 E-5
11.	Peroxidizability index	PI	28.2135513
12.	n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA		31.824611

$$\text{EPA+DHA} = 4.0343 \text{ E-6 } \% \equiv 8.53860000 \text{ E-8 g/100g} \\ \equiv 8.5386 \text{ mg/100g}$$

Phospholipids levels of the chicken eggshells

The phospholipids level of the sample can be seen in Table 6. Reasonable levels of the various members of PLDs can be observed in Table 6. However, phosphatidylcholine (PC) was the most concentrated member with a value of 75.19708 mg/100g (69.8750%) and this is distantly followed by phosphatidylinositol (PI) at 12.42272 mg/100g (11.54350%); the remaining percentages were shared between PE, LPC and PS; total PLDs was 107.61661 mg/100g.

Table 6. Phospholipids composition of the chicken egg shell (mg/100g) and their percentage position

S/N	Phospholipids	Amount	Percentage (position)
1.	Phosphatidylethanolamine	10.96305	10.1871 (3rd)
2.	Phosphatidylcholine	75.19708	69.8750 (1st)
3.	Phosphatidylserine	2.80557	2.6050 (5th)
4.	Lysophosphatidylcholine	6.22619	5.7874 (4th)
5.	Phosphatidylinositol	12.42272	11.54350 (2nd)
6.	Total	107.61661	100

Sterols composition in the sample

Seven sterol members were listed in Table 7. However, only cholesterol has low recognisable level of 9.06050 mg/100g and a percentage level of 99.99691%. Other members in Table 7 shared a total value of 0.0028 mg/100g or 0.00309024% (this is highly negligible).

Table 7. Sterols composition of the chicken eggshell (mg/100g) and percentage value of cholesterol

S/N	Sterols	Quantity	Cholesterol (%)
1.	Cholesterol	9.06050	99.99691
2.	Cholestanol	9.78665E-5	
3.	Ergosterol	4.51088E-5	
4.	Campesterol	2.75975E-5	
5.	Stigmasterol	5.24629E-5	
6.	5-Avenasterol	3.99186E-5	
7.	Sitosterol	1.95363E-5	
8.	Totals	9.060978	

Discussion

In Table 1, the low value of CF (2.55 g/100g) may be a characteristic of some poultry eggshells. Adeyeye [21] had reported the following CFs in some poultry eggshells common in Nigeria: 2.54 g/100g (francolin), 5.32 g/100g (duck) and 8.54 g/100g (turkey). From literature values, francolin of 2.54 g/100g is slightly below the present report of 2.55 g/100g by just 0.01 g/100g (0.392%). Also the calculated (theoretical) FAs values would follow this trend: 2.1165 g/100g (hen's eggshells), 2.1082 g/100g (francolin), 4.4156 g/100g (duck) and 7.0882 g/100g (turkey). The total other lipids (OLs) in the present study was 0.4335 g/100g. From the literature cited above, the trend would be: 0.4318 g/100g (very close to the hen's value of 0.4335 g/100g) for francolin, 0.9044 g/100g (duck) and 1.4518 g/100g (turkey). Since energy is a reflection of the FAs composition, in both CF, TFAs and OLs, the trend in energy would follow the above observations.

The SFA group shows some similarities with egg (whole, edible portion, raw, wet weight) of the hen. C12:0 in shell is 3.3864E-7 g but it is 0 g in the whole egg; C14:0 in shell is 4.4914E-4 g but it is 0.033 g (3.3E-2 g) in whole egg; C16:0 is 0.4043 g in shell, it is 2.231 g (much higher) in whole egg; C18:0 is 0.2699 g in shell but it is 0.811 g in whole egg. C24:0 in shell is 1.1217E-6 g but 0 g in whole egg. Total SFA in shell is 0.6746 g but it is 3.126 g in whole egg. In most samples C16:0 usually takes the highest position in total SFA and usually followed by

C18:0. In this study, the percentage of C16:0 in the SFA was 59.93% whereas the value in C18:0 was 40.01%. C16:0:C18:0 was 1.50:1.00. In the whole egg, C16:0 was 71.37% and 25.93% in the C18:0; ratio is 2.75:1.00 [31]. Quail whole egg has: C12:0 (0 g), C14:0 (0.053 g), C16:0 (2.666 g), C18:0 (0.838 g), C24:0 ~ [data not available for tilde (~) items], Σ SFA (3.557 g). Total trans FAs was 1.22021E-5% in the shell whereas it is 0.026 g in the whole egg but it is ~ in the quail whole egg. The trace level of trans FAs in the shell is nutritionally good as trans FAs are nutritionally deleterious to the consumer.

The MUFA (cis) total of the shell came majorly from C18:1 cis-9 (22.703339%, 0.4805 g/100 g, 50.50%) and C18:1 cis-6 (19.893537%, 0.2729 g/100 g, 44.25%) of the total MUFA (cis). Σ MUFA (cis) in whole egg (hen) is 3.658 g and 4.324 g (in quail whole egg). However, the only major contributor in the whole egg is C18:1 cis-9 (3.388 g, 92.62%) but is ~in C18:1 cis-9 in the quail egg [31]. The Σ PUFA in the sample is 23.17% (0.4904 g); this is about 25.66% (9.11 g) of the whole hen's egg and 37.04% (3.851 g) of the whole quail's egg. C18:2 cis-9,12 (21.092293%) formed the highest and most significant part of the Σ PUFA forming about 91.03%; C20:4 cis-5,8,11,14 contributed just 4.499% (the second highest). ALA is 0.036 g in hen's egg and ~ in the quail egg but 0.0150 g in hen's eggshell. LA occupied the highest position in hen's egg and the quail egg. EPA is 0 g in both hen's egg, quail egg and hen's eggshell. DPA is 0 g in the hen's eggshell and the quail egg but it is 0.058 g in the whole hen's egg [31].

From Table 3, the total FAs as food was 2.1165 g/100 g; this is equivalent to 19.0486 kcal/100 g (see Table 1). The contribution to this total energy from relevant groups were: 6.0714 kcal/100 g (31.87%) from Σ SFA; 8.5640 kcal/100 g (44.96%) from Σ MUFA (cis); 4.2786 kcal/100 g (22.46%) from Σ n-6 PUFA and 0.1346 kcal/100 g (0.7066%) from ALA. This meant that 12.9772 kcal/100 g or 68.13% of energy would come from the unsaturated fatty acids (Σ UFAs) whereas 31.87% would come from the Σ SFA. It follows that the bulk of the FAs energy would come from the Σ UFA. This 68.13% UFA energy would make the eggshell more favourable in enhancing the animal feed formulated from it.

The insignificant FAs in Table 4 is just for noting as they do not normally affect seriously the quality of the eggshells.

Assessing the indices of IA, IT, H/h, HPI, UI, EPA+DHA, FLQ, LA/ALA, PUFA/SFA, TFA, n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA, and PI can provide information regarding the different effects that individual FAs could have on human health, particularly on the likelihood of an increased incidence of atherosclerosis, blood clots development, atheroma and thrombus formation [26, 32]. The health indices of the fatty acids of the sample can be pursued from Table 5.

The IA characterises the atherogenic potential of FA [26]. The IA indicates the relationship between the sum of SFAs and the sum of UFAs. The main classes of SFAs, which include C12:0, C14:0 and C16:0, are considered pro-atherogenic (they favour the adhesion of lipids to cells of the circulatory and immunological systems [33]). UFAs are considered to be anti-atherogenic as they inhibit the accumulation of plaque and reduce the levels of phospholipids, cholesterol and esterified FAs [33]. Therefore, the consumption of foods or products with a lower IA can reduce the levels of total cholesterol and LDL-C in human blood plasma [34]. The eggshell IA (0.2816) is better than the value of 0.39 observed in the Eskimo diet. It is within the value of 0.165–0.634 in chicken (Caribro Vishal) [35] but better than the value of 0.372–0.390 in chicken (purchased from a hatchery and poultry farm) [36].

The IT characterises the thrombogenic potential of FAs, indicating the tendency to form clots in blood vessels and provides the contribution of different FAs, which denotes the relationship between the pro-thrombogenic FAs (C12:0, C14:0 and C16:0) and the anti-thrombogenic FAs (MUFAs and the n-3 and n-6 families) [26]. Therefore, the consumption of foods or products with a lower IT is beneficial for CVH. The present IT value is 0.889. This value is close to the value of 0.755 – 0.784 in chicken (purchased from a hatchery and poultry farm) [36] but within the value of 0.288–1.694 in chicken (Caribro Vishal) [35].

The H/h characterises the relationship between hypocholesterolemic FA (cis-C18:1 and PUFA) and hypercholesterolemic FA. The sample H/h is 2.399. This value is lower than the range of 2.658–2.786 in chicken (purchased from a hatchery and poultry farm) [36] but higher than in lamb (Merino Branco) at 1.92 [37], lamb (Ile de France x Merino Branco) at 2.01 [37], and cattle (Nellore cattle) at 1.56–2.08 [38].

The HPI is the inverse of the IA. It is currently mainly used in research on dairy products such as milk [39] and

cheese [40]. The HPI in the sample is 3.551. The literature value range from 0.16 to 0.68 (much lower than the present result) [40, 39, 41]. Food products with a high HPI value are assumed to be more beneficial to human health.

The UI indicates the degree of unsaturation in lipids. Unlike Σ UFA and Σ PUFA, different UFAs have different weights in the UI. This index indicates the impact of highly unsaturated FA and does not ignore the impact of FA that have a low degree of unsaturation. In general, the UI more comprehensively reflects the proportion of FA with different degrees of unsaturation in the total FA composition of a species. The UI value of sample is 94.1946. Colombo et al. [42] have suggested that the FAs with a high degree of unsaturation in a membrane lipid can maintain fluidity at relative low temperature. The UI value of seaweeds varied widely from 45 to 368.68, and may be closely related to the species [2]. Literature UI in meat are: Pig [Pietrain x (Duroc x Landrace)], 111-124 [43] and Dry-cured ham [Landrace x Large White (25% Pietrain) pig], 73±6 [44]; dairy products: Milk of (New Zealand x California) white rabbit, 86-120 [45].

EPA + DHA and FLQ are of no consequence in this study as they contain similar value of 4.0343E-6%.

The LA/ALA ratio in the sample is 29.84503. The Definitions and Nutrient Composition section of the Guidelines for Infant Formula published by Food Standards Australia New Zealand (FSANZ) sets the minimum and maximum proportions of LA and ALA, and specifies an LA/ALA ratio within 5:1–15:1 [2]. There is no literature match of LA/ALA in the sample. Similar high value of 31.824611 was observed in n-6/n-3 PUFA.

TFA value was very low at 1.2202E-5%. Since TFA is not needed nutritionally, its negligible value here is a nutritional advantage.

PUFA/SFA is an index normally used to assess the impact of diet on cardiovascular health (CVH). It hypothesizes that all PUFA in the diet can depress low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and lower level of serum cholesterol whereas all SFAs contribute to high levels of serum cholesterol. Thus, the higher this ratio, the more positive the effect. PUFA/SFA in the sample is 0.7269. Usually PUFA/SFA value should equal to 1.0–1.5 (≥ 0.40), the sample result falls into this range. The sample result falls within the values of 0.308–2.042 in chicken (Caribro Vishal) [35] but close to the values of 0.926–0.945 in chicken (purchased from a hatchery and poultry farm) [36].

The PI of the sample is 28.2135513. The lowest and highest peroxidizability index (PI) was estimated in flax and hemp seeds, respectively (80–90) to reduce the risk of CVD [46]. Value result is very low to 80–90. This means the sample has very low peroxidation potential and has a high keeping quality.

The various PLDs values are displayed in Table 6. PLDs are involved in the following functions: forms cell membranes; involved in selective permeability; cellular protection; signal transduction and emulsification. PC formed the largest content at 69.9% of the total value of PLDs. It forms about 40–60% of PLDs in eukaryotic cell membranes and is a crucial structural component of cells and lipoproteins. In human bile, PC is the predominant PLDs species, making up 80–95% of the total PLDs. Second highest is the PI at 11.5%. It makes up 3–10% of total cell membranes. It is a precursor for signaling molecules, particularly inositol phosphates (IPs) like PI(4,5)P2. PE constitutes about 10.2% in the sample but it constitutes 15–25% of total lipids in mammalian cells. Next in consideration is LPC which formed 5.79% of the concentration. Healthy individuals have plasma LPC levels ranging from 125 to 143 nmol/ml; it is a component of oxidized low-density lipoprotein (oxLDL), a marker of cardiovascular disease. LPC in human synovial fluid is LPC 16:0, accounting for 42%–49% of all LPCs. PS is 2.6% of the total PLDs. It makes up 2–10% total PLDs in mammalian cells, but is concentrated in the brain and other tissues. It is a supplement for improving cognitive function, making up to 10–20% in the total brain PLDs [47].

The cholesterol content of the sample is 9.06059 mg/100g out of 9.06078 mg/100g; therefore cholesterol makes up to 99.99691% of the sterols. The cholesterol in the hen's egg is 372 mg and 844 mg in the quail whole egg [31]. In the present results, campesterol, stigmasterol, beta-sitosterol, 5-avenasterol, ergosterol and cholestanol values range from 1.95363E-5 to 9.78665E-5 mg/100g. Except for the cholesterol, other sterols in both hen's whole egg and quail's whole egg have ~ items. [~ Data not available for tilde (~) items.] [31].

Conclusion

The study was based on the evaluation of lipid profile of the local (free range) hen's eggshells. The crude fat (CF), theoretical fatty acids (FAs) and other lipids (OLs) have this trend: CF/FAs/OLs (g/100g) = 2.55 > 2.1165 > 0.4335 respectively (representing food value in FAs and OLs) with the corresponding energy (kcal/100g) of 22.95

> 19.05 > 3.90 respectively. The FAs/CF (%) was 83.0 whereas OLs/CF (%) was 17.0 and OLs/TFA (%) was 20.48. The classic indices were Σ SFA (31.9%), Σ MUFA (trans) (1.22E-5%), Σ MUFA(cis) (44.95%), Σ n-6 PUFA (22.46%) and Σ n-3 PUFA (0.707%) of total FAs in each case. For the health indices, the IA is below the Eskimo diet; IT is slightly above the Eskimo diet (it is beneficial for a healthy CVH); H/h is high and it is beneficial to the human health (it has high hypocholesterolemic potential); UI shows moderate FA unsaturation; sample is deficient in EPA + DHA, LA/ALA and n-6 PUFA/n-3 PUFA were unduly high due to very low ALA; PUFA/SFA is within the range of 1.0–1.5; PI showed low potential peroxidability index. The PLDs values followed the following trend in percentage: PC (75.2%) > PI (11.5%) > PE (10.2%) > LPC (5.79%) > PS (2.61%) based on total PLDs (108 mg/100g). The CF and FAs values quantity are in line with many literature values. These various results put the hen's eggshells in a good stead for animal feed formulation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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